

Analysis of the content of The Netherlands Research Portal

Author: Alessia Bardi (CNR-ISTI), OpenAIRE CONNECT Service Manager
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Executive Summary

The Netherlands Research Portal (<https://connect.openaire.eu>) was set up in July 2023 in response to the shutdown of the NARCIS national portal in January 2023.

NARCIS is one of the data sources aggregated by OpenAIRE. After its shutdown, Dutch repositories were supported at providing their content directly to OpenAIRE.

Records from NARCIS are still in the OpenAIRE Graph to ensure repositories had enough time to register into OpenAIRE.

The analysis verifies if, in March 2024, NARCIS can be deleted from the list of aggregated sources of OpenAIRE without any major loss of metadata about Dutch products.

The analysis reveals that the portal includes:

- 3.707.969 publications published before June 2023
- 1.721.354 are collected from the selected repositories and NARCIS
- 353.370 are collected only from the selected repositories
- 1.099.124 are collected only from NARCIS

Because 1M records collected only from NARCIS is about 33% of the content in the portal, we further analysed the subset to suggest strategies to cover the gap.

The analysis on the data source aggregation suggests there is a mismatch between the configuration of the Netherlands Research Portal and the OpenAIRE aggregation status. As detailed in the spreadsheet deposited together with this report (NL data 2024-03-26), several sources are missing from the configuration, including Maastricht and Vrije University Amsterdam. Other repositories in the configuration are instead not harvested by OpenAIRE. Probably those repositories were previously harvested and added to the configuration. Then the repo manager asked to migrate from the old repo to the new CRIS system and nobody updated the gateway configuration accordingly.

The proposal is therefore to update the configuration adding the missing sources and replicate the analysis after the next update of the OpenAIRE Graph (April 2024).

Methodology

The CNR team of OpenAIRE analyzed the version of the OpenAIRE Graph available in the OpenAIRE portals in March 2024. The graph was updated on 2024-03-21.

The Netherlands portal include research products:

- Collected or hosted by data sources listed at <https://netherlands.openaire.eu/search/find/dataproviders>
- Funded by any of the projects listed at <https://netherlands.openaire.eu/search/find/projects>
- Authored by people affiliated with a Dutch organisation in the provided list. The list of Dutch organisations is spreadsheet deposited together with this report (NL data 2024-03-26).

Results

1. How many records are in the Netherlands Research Portal?
4.521.201
2. Browse by result type

Number of records	Type
3.805.872	publication
513.491	dataset
200.036	other
1.802	software

3. How many publications published before June 2023 are in the Netherlands Research Portal?
3.707.969
4. How many publications published before June 2023 in the Netherlands Research Portal are collected from NARCIS
2.820.478
5. How many publications published before June 2023 in the Netherlands Research Portal are collected from any of the selected NL repository
2.074.724
6. How many publications published before June 2023 in the Netherlands Research Portal are collected from any of the selected NL repositories AND NARCIS?
1.721.354
7. How many publications published before June 2023 in the Netherlands Research Portal are collected from NARCIS and NOT from any of the selected NL repository
1.099.124

Of those:

- 107.514 can be found in OpenAIRE from other sources.
 - About 6K are tagged for the NL research portal because of reasons different from being collected from NARCIS
 - 4K records with DOI are included in the portal because of affiliations to one of the selected organisations
 - 1K records with a PubMed id are included in the portal because of affiliations to one of the selected organisations
 - 1K records with DOI are included in the portal because funded by one of the selected projects
 - The remaining 100K are in the OpenAIRE Graph but they are included in the portal only because of NARCIS. We probably could include more with the increase of affiliation information in OpenAIRE and a revision of the list of selected organisations (see [NL data 2024-03-26](#))
- The rest could not be found in any other sources of OpenAIRE

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repo manager asked to migrate from the old repo to the new CRIS system and nobody updated the gateway configuration accordingly.

8. How many publications published before June 2023 in the Netherlands Research Portal are collected from any of the selected NL repository and NOT NARCIS
353.370
9. Reason why publications published after June 2023 have been added to the Netherlands Research Portal

Number of records	Provenance	Provenance explanation
3.091.710	community:datasource	Pubs from one of the selected sources
509.005	result:community:organization	Affiliations
60.183	result:community:semrel	Pubs linked to other NL product with "supplements/isSupplementedBy" semantics
34.739	community:datasource, result:community:project	
7.228	result:community:project	Pubs funded by one of the selected projects
5.082	result:community:organization, result:community:project	
19	user:claim	Linked by users
2	user:claim, community:datasource	